

Insulin Sensitivity Estimation Using Long Short-Term Memory Neural Network to Guide Insulin Dosing in Intensive Care

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Abstract: A significant portion of patients in the intensive care unit experience abnormal blood glucose levels, making it necessary to use insulin dosing to regulate the physiological blood glucose range. The STAR – StochasticTARgetted glucose control protocol is a clinical system used for insulin dosing designed as a tight glycemic control protocol that uses the patient's insulin sensitivity to assess their current condition. Forecasting a patient's insulin sensitivity in STAR is essential for planning effective treatment, where guided predictions are crucial for reducing treatment risk. Several methods have been adopted to predict insulin sensitivity, along with particular metrics to assess how well each method performs. In the STAR treatment, the challenge is determining the 90% confidence interval of the future insulin sensitivity of the patients, allowing the calculation of the clinical outcomes of the alternative treatments. This research proposed a Recurrent Neural Network model for predicting insulin sensitivity and comparing the result with the previous feed-forward model. Results demonstrate that the proposed model has better prediction accuracy than the feed-forward model and the one currently used in STAR. The promising results positioned the adopted model as a candidate for in-silico validation before clinical use.

Introduction

Personalised Intensive Care Unit (ICU) care is increasingly important to enhance patient outcomes and optimise productivity [1]. The original Stochastic TARgetted (STAR) glycemic control protocol is a clinically validated method that employs a model-based approach relying on the Intensive Control Insulin-Nutrition -Glucose (ICING) model to assess insulin sensitivity (SI) [2].

The ICING model, shown in Figure 1, represents the human body's metabolic system [3]. The ICING model defines the patient's blood glucose response based on nutrition and insulin dosage.

This model is applied uniquely in the STAR protocol: all parameters are kept constant except for SI. This approach allows the protocol to capture changes in the patient's condition by adjusting the SI parameter only. STAR protocol uses the conditional density function to determine the likelihood of future SI values within a 90% confidence interval for the next 1, 2 and 3 hours, based on current $SI(t)$ [4], [5].

Many methods were used to forecast the stochastic data. LSTM, a widely used artificial intelligence technique, has proven effective in predicting biological processes with stochastic behaviour, as shown in studies [6], [7]. LSTM have the ability to control how information flows in and out, helping it decide which details to keep, which to update, and which to forget [8]. The strength of this approach lies in its ability to forecast the statistical properties of a stochastic variable, making it particularly well-suited for estimating the 90% confidence interval of future SI values.

This research aims to improve the efficiency of the STAR protocol by introducing a new approach for forecasting SI using Recurrent Neural Network-based (RNN) based on Log Short Term Memory (LSTM), then validating the result using clinical data from STAR to verify its ability to forecast the SI in three-time horizons.

Methods and Data

The clinical and technical challenge in predicting SI lies in estimating a range of future possibilities rather than a single mean or median value. In the stochastic model approach, SI is represented using a conditional distribution where $SI(t)$ is the condition, and $SI(t+1)$ is the target variable. This conditional distribution is generated by assuming that each pair of values, $SI(t)$ and $SI(t+1)$, is drawn from a normal distribution of similar points, as shown in Figure 2. The 90% confidence interval is then defined as the range within this conditional normal distribution across multiple data point pairs.

The study utilised a dataset of ICU patients treated with the STAR protocol. Furthermore, the LSTM model was proposed to predict SI using a particular loss function, directly targeting specific quantiles rather than the entire distribution. To ensure model robustness, k-fold cross-validation was applied. Performance evaluation relied on relevant metrics assessing the model's effectiveness in predicting SI. Moreover, the current LSTM model behaviour was compared to the previous work using a feed-forward model [9].

Figure 1 A graphical representation of the ICING pharmacokinetic model [2].

Long Short-Term Memory network, LSTM, is a special kind of neural network that's especially good at understanding data sequences. It's a type of RNN designed to remember important information over long sequences and forget irrelevant details. These features make it preferable for healthcare prediction applications [7], especially for extensive medical datasets [6]. Each LSTM cell has gates that control how information flows in and out, helping it decide which details to keep, which to update, and which to forget. This ability to selectively remember and forget significantly improves over traditional RNNs, which struggle with long sequences and often forget essential information too soon [8].

Clinical data analysis: the data were collected from patients treated with the STAR protocol, covering the period from 2011 to 2022. Patients with fewer than 12 hours of data were excluded, resulting in a final cohort of 2,349 patients. SI values were computed for every hour of patient stay. The training-testing dataset comprised 116,473 data points [9], with 99.9% of SI values below $2.8e-3$ L/mU/min.

The k-fold cross-validation method was applied to analyse the results. The validation shows the practical performance of the technique on unseen data and how the model depends on the training data selection.

Metrics: Three clinically relevant metrics were defined to evaluate the proposed methods [10].

Success Rate: Measures the statistical probability that a data point is in the predicted, relevant 90% confidence interval. A higher success rate leads to more prediction accuracy.

Interval Ratio: The width of the confidence interval of the proposed method can be compared with the widths from a reference predictor. A narrower confidence interval will increase the prediction accuracy.

I-Score: The success rate and the interval ratio are in a trade-off relation. I-score measures this trade-off with a ratio. The goal is to get a high I-score over the entire prediction horizon.

Figure 2 Scatter plot of the SI(t)-SI(t+1) pairs. On the sides, the histogram of the matching parameter can be seen.

Results

Table 1 shows the prediction evaluation of the LSTM model, interval ratio, success rate, and I-score for the average of k-fold cross-validation for prediction SI in three time horizons. Interestingly, the prediction accuracy has moderate change over entire prediction horizons.

Figure 3 shows the result of 90% confidence intervals of the LSTM model visualised over the entire SI horizons, i.e. SI (t+1, +2 and +3). The dark red dots represent the original (SI(t); SI (t+1, +2 and +3))) data points, the orange line represents the 95th percentiles, and the blue line represents the 5th percentiles over the entire physiologically relevant range of SI. The figure shows the projection of the results to a 2D space defined by SI(t) and SI (t+1, +2, and +3). Most original data points corresponding to the treatment hours fall between the blue and orange lines. The dashed blue line represents the STAR prediction border used as a reference.

Table 2 shows the results of previous work presented in [9], where the feed-forward quantile-based neural network model was used, and the model was trained and tested with the same data, training, testing, and validation environment. The feed-forward quantile-based has good prediction accuracy for the SI (t+1) horizon. However, the prediction accuracy was decreased while the SI horizon increased, i.e. (t+1 and t+2).

Figure 4 shows the comparative analysis of the current adopted LSTM model and the quantile-based in previous work [9]. The bar plot addressed the matrices evaluated success rate, interval ratio, and I-scours results.

The average bar represents the average value of each parameter in three time horizons, while the error bar represents the standard deviation of SI (t+1, +2, and +3). The comparison results show that the current adopted LSTM model has a narrower confidence interval for the entire prediction horizon, higher prediction accuracy for SI (t+1, +2), and lower deviation in the results.

Table 1 SI Prediction accuracy values for three time horizons based on the LSTM model.

SI horizons	Interval ratio	Success rate	I-score
SI(t+1)	0.776	0.904	1.319
SI(t+2)	0.771	0.801	1.012
SI(t+3)	0.752	0.750	0.931

Table 2 Statistical evaluation result of the feed-forward quantile-based SI prediction model [9].

SI horizons	Interval ratio	Success rate	I-score
SI(t+1)	0.776	0.928	1.409
SI(t+2)	1.309	0.954	0.927
SI(t+3)	1.114	0.904	0.908

Figure 3 The resulting percentile values (5%, blue line and 95%, orange line) of the SI domain for SI (t + 1), SI (t + 2), and SI (t + 3) in the function of SI (t) by using LSTM model. The prediction used by STAR is shown in the dashed blue line.

However, the feed-forward quantile-based model has a better success rate, but the prediction confidence interval became broader in the high prediction horizons, i.e. (t+2) and (t+3), causing low prediction accuracy.

Discussion

Based on the results in Figure 3 and the statistical parameters in Table 1, the model addressed a higher prediction accuracy for entire prediction horizons and performed a narrower interval ratio of less than (0.8). It can be seen in Figure 3 that in a relatively large region of SI, the upper border of the confidence interval moved closer to the medium value. These results could be valuable to the STAR protocol as it allows the use of higher insulin dosing, driving the patient's BG to the normal range faster.

Analysing Figure 4 shows that the adopted LSTM model improves the 90% confidence interval prediction accuracy over the feed-forward quantile-based model [9]. The proposed LSTM model addressed tight prediction accuracy results in the entire prediction horizon.

The prediction success rate is (0.9 – 0.75), whereas the prediction confidence interval remains narrower than the predictor used in STAR protocol (0.768 –

0.771) over the entire prediction horizon, which pushes the prediction accuracy to stay at a high level, and results I-score between 1.319 and 0.931.

Figure 4 Bar plot compares the results of the LSTM and the feed-forward quantile-based models. The error bar attached to the average bar represents the standard deviation for SI(t+1), SI(t+2) and SI(t+3).

This improvement may significantly benefit clinical applications with higher prediction accuracy, especially in the case of wider SI horizons. Hence, the narrower confidence interval will allow more aggressive insulin and nutrition administration and, thus, an earlier return to normal glycemic ranges, which are shown to provide the best outcomes.

In summary, these results show the potential of the LSTM model as a first step towards using these methods to invoke more efficient network topologies and in-silico validation. Thus, the results justify further study and optimisation.

Conclusions

Insulin sensitivity prediction methods using an LSTM model were proposed, and their applicability in glycemic control protocol, especially in STAR, was analysed. The suggested method's prediction accuracy was enhanced by providing specific predictions for selected quantiles, offering a more detailed approximation of the conditional probability distribution function. The most considerable benefit of the LSTM model for SI prediction is that it provides a narrow confidence interval by decreasing the upper broader of the interval. The significantly narrower confidence interval potentially leads to higher insulin rates in clinical treatment and thus further reduces the clinical risk of care. A more general outcome of the study demonstrates the applicability of artificial intelligence, specifically the LSTM neural network-based model, for patient state prediction in model-based clinical treatment.

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